

TEMPLE OF GAURĪ-SOMANĀTHA AT MANDHATA, DISTT. KHANDWĀ, M. P.

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Mandhata is one of the most celebrated places of Śaiva pilgrimage. It is located 75 kms. north-west of Khandwa in the district of the same name in Madhya Pradesh. The nearest Railway station is Onkareshwar road on metre gauge western railway connecting Ajmer with Khandwa. The distance from the Railway station to Mandhata is 11 kms and regular buses ply from the Railway station to Mandhata. Mandhata is connected with Khandwa, Indore Maheshwar and Ujjain by bus.

Mandhata is a village situated partly on the south bank and partly on an island in river Narmada. Some scholars have tried to identify Mandhata with ancient Māhishmatī. Mandhata has a number of temples. The main temple is dedicated to Onkareshwar. The temple is dedicated to one of the twelve Jyotirlingas.

The temple of Gauri Somanātha stands to the north of the island. It has a star-shaped plan, and stands on a spacious platform on the northern hill. It consists on plan of a *saptaratha* sanctum and a vestibule (pl. I). The sanctum enshrines a black stone polished *līṅga* (pl. II). The temple faces east. In front of the vestibule is a platform on which is installed a seated Nandi. The sanctum as well as the vestibule are two-storeyed. The first floor is approached by a flight of steps on the east.

The sanctum-doorway shows seven jambs or *sākhas*. The lower portion of the right flank of the doorway shows :

1. A female standing in *tribhāṅga* under a lotus-parsol and carrying *kaṭi* and upraised. Her left hand has been chopped off.

2. A female standing in *tribhaṅga* under a lotus-parsol and carrying indistinct and *kalāṣa*. Her left breast has been chopped off.
3. A female standing in *tribhaṅga* under a lotus-parsol and carrying *kaṭi* and *bijapūrka*. Her right hand has been chopped off.
4. A niche composed of two circular pilasters and containing an image of a four-armed *śaiva dvārapāla* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying indistinct, *triśūla*, *sarpa*, and *bijapūraka*.
5. A female standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *kaṭi* and *kalāṣa*.
6. A female standing in *tribhaṅga* in a recess.
7. A male standing cross-legged and carrying concealed and a bow.

The left flank of the doorway shows (1) A female standing in *tribhaṅga* under a lotus-parsol and carrying upraised and *kaṭi* (2) A female standing in *tribhaṅga* under a lotus-parsol and carrying flower and *kaṭi* (3) A female standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *kalāṣa* and *kaṭi*. She stands under a lotus-parsol. (4) A niche composed of two circular pilasters and containing an image of four-armed *śaiva-dvārapāla* standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *kalāṣa* *triśūla*, *sarpa* and *gadā*. The *gadā* in his lower left hand has been chopped off. (5) A female standing in *tribhaṅga* under a lotus-parsol and carrying upraised and *kaṭi*. (6) A female standing in *tribhaṅga* in a recess and carrying upraised and *kaṭi* (7) A male standing cross-legged and carrying bow and indistinct.

The doorway is of overdoor design. The lintel of the doorway of the sanctum shows four-armed Gaṇeśa seated in *lalitāsana* on the *lalāṭa-bimba*.

The door-sill of the sanctum-doorway shows a *mandāraka* in the centre decorated with bold lotus-scrolls. The *mandāraka* is flanked on either side by a *kirttimukha* with open mouth. Inside the sanctum is also seen an image of four-armed Pārvati standing in *sambhaṅga* (pl. III).

The vestibule is decorated with two hollow niche-shrines composed of two rectangular pilasters and surmounted by a *makara-toraṇa*. The niche-shrine in the southern wall contains a *śivaliṅga* made of polished black sandstone and measuring 0.65 mt. high. The niche-shrine in the northern wall is vacant at present. The ceiling of the sanctum consists of five receding octagons and is decorated on the top with geometrical and floral designs. (pl. IV).

The pītha of the temple consists of the following mouldings from bottom upwards, (1) plain *bhīṭṭa*, (2) *bhīṭṭa* decorated with half-chaitya arche-design, (3) *jādyakumbha*, (4) *karṇikā*, (5) *kapota* and (6) *grasspaṭṭikā*. The *adhishṭhāna* mouldings show from bottom upwards. (1) *Khura* (2) *kumbha* divided into two segments by a median band

Pl. I. Gauri Somanātha temple, General view from south east (M. P.)

Pl II. Śivaliṅga, Gauri-Somanātha temple (M. P.)

Pl. III Pārvati, Gaurī-Somanātha temple (M. P.)

Pl. IV. Ceiling of the sanctum, Gauri-Somanātha temple (M. P.)

Pl. V. The mouldings and the Jaṅghā on the northern facade
Gauri-Somanātha temple (M. P.)

of diamonds and rosettes and decorated with diamond and chess designs in niches surmounted by a *chaitya*-arches, (3) *kalāṣa* decorated with a median band of diamonds and rosettes, (4) *kapota* decorated with *kuṇḍūs*, (5) A plain *kalāṣa*. Above this rests the *jaṅghā* divided into two segments by a *karṇikā* (pl. V). The upper portion of the *jaṅghā* is decorated with *chaitya*-arches and half lotus medallions. The *bhadra* on the *jaṅghā* shows an image of a deity in a niche. Above the *jaṅghā* rest the *varaṇḍikā* mouldings. The *varaṇḍikā* mouldings are surmounted by the *sikhara*. The *sikhara* is divided into seven storeys by *bhūmi-āmalakas*.

SCULPTURES ON THE SOUTHERN JAṅGHĀ FACADE :

The *bhadra* on the southern *jaṅghā* facade is decorated with a niche composed of two circular pilasters and surmounted by a *makaratorāṇa*. The niche contained an image of four-armed Kubera standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varada-cum-akshamālā*, purse, purse and *kalāṣa*. He wears *karaṇḍa-mukuṣa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra* long *mālā* and a lower garment fastened by a *mekhalā*. The mount elephant is shown seated on his left.

2. The *kumbha* moulding of the *adhishṭhāna* shows on the *bhadra* a niche composed of two rectangular pilasters and surmounted by a *chhādyā*. It is decorated with diamonds and lotus designs on the top. The niche contains an image of four-armed Vaishṇavi seated on Garuḍa and carrying broken *chakra* and *gadā*. The head of Garuḍa and both the legs of Vaishṇavi have been chopped off. She wears *kirīṭamukuṣa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas* and a *sāri* fastened by a *mekhalā*.

3. A niche on the lower portion of the *sikhara* and above the *varaṇḍikā* mouldings is lying vacant at present.

4. A niche on the seventh i.e. the top most storey of the *sikhara* contains an image of four-armed Śiva standing in *tribhaṅga* and holding a *khaṭvāṅga* in his upper right hand.

NICHE ON THE SOUTHERN WALL OF THE VESTIBULE :

A niche composed of four rectangular pilasters and surmounted by an *udgama* decorated with diamond designs is seen on the southern wall of the vestibule. It contains an image of four-armed Gaṇeśa seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *aṅkuṣa*, *paraśu*, *padma*, and *modaka-pātra*. He wears *karaṇḍamukuṣa*. He is pot-bellied and a snake is tied around his belly. His trunk rests on the *modakapātra*.

NICHES ON THE WESTERN FACADE :

The western facade of the temple shows four niches one on the *Kumbha*, other on

the *jaṅghā*, the third on the lower portion of the *sikhara* above the *jaṅghā* and the fourth on the seventh storey of the *sikhara* :

1. The niche on the *bhadra* of the *kumbha* consists of four rectangular pilasters and is surmounted by an *udgama* decorated with lotus and diamond designs. The niche contains an image of four-armed Maheśvarī seated on a bull. All of her hands except the right upper one have been chopped off. She carries a *triśūla* in her upper right hand. She wears *Jaṭāmukuṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas* and *sāri* fastened by a *mekhalā*. Her breasts and legs have been chopped off.
2. The niche on the *bhadra* of the *jaṅghā* is composed of two circular pilasters and is surmounted by a *makaratorana*. It contains an image of four-armed Śiva standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varada-cum-akshamālā*, *triśūla*, *khaṭvāṅga* and *gadā*. He wears *jaṭāmukuta*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra yajñopavita*, *keyuras*, *valayas* a long *mālā* and a lower garment fastened by a *mekhalā*.
3. A niche on the lower position of the *sikhara* above the *varaṇḍika* mouldings, contains an image of four-armed Śiva standing in *sambhaṅga* and holding a *triśūla* and *śarṇa* in his upper right and left hands. The image is made of black stone.
4. A niche on the seventh storey of the *sikhara* contains an image of Umā-Maheśvara seated.

NICHES ON THE NORTHERN FACADE

The northern facade shows four niches like the other facades on the *bhadra* :

1. The niche on the *kumbha* is composed of four rectangular pilasters and is surmounted by an *udgama* decorated with diamond designs. The niche contains an image of four-armed Brahmī seated in *lalitāsana* on a *pītha*. She wears *jaṭāmukuṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *keyuras*, *valayas* and a lower garment fastened by a *mekhalā*. She carries *varada-cum-akshamālā*, *śruka*, *pustaka* and *ghaṭa*.
2. A niche on the *bhadra* of the *jaṅghā* composed of two circular pilasters and surmounted by a *makara-toraṇa*. It contains an image of four-armed Brahmā standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varada*, chopped off spiral lotus-salk and *ghata*. He is bearded, pot-bellied and has long moustaches. He wears *jaṭāmukuṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *hāra*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, a lower garment fastened by a *mekhalā* and a long *mālā*. The seated mount swan with chopped head is shown on his left.
3. A niche on the lower portion of the *sikhara* and above the *varaṇḍikā* mouldings is lying vacant at present.

4. niche on the seventh storey of the *sikhara* contains an image of four-armed Devi standing in *tribhaṅga* and holding a *gadā* in her upper right hand.

SCULPTURES ON THE NORTHERN JANGHĀ FACADE

1. A niche composed of two circular pilasters and surmounted by a *makara-toraṇa*. It contains an image of four-armed Śiva standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varada-cum-akshamālā*, *triśūla*, *sarpa* and *gadā*. He wears an elongated *jaṭāmukuṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyuras*, *valayas*, a long *mālā* and a lower garment fastened by a *mekhalā*. The seated mount bull with upraised head is shown on his right.
2. A niche composed of two circular pilasters and surmounted by *makara toraṇa*. It contains an image of four-armed Śiva standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *bijṅpūraka*, *ḍamaru*, *khaṭvāṅga* and *kapāla*. He wears *karaṇḍamukuṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *yajñopavita*, *keyuras*, *valayas* and a lower garment fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels.
3. A dancing *apsaras* shown under a lotus in a recess. Both of her hands have been chopped off.
4. An *apsaras* standing under a spiral lotus-stalk in a recess. Her right hand is in *kaṭi* while her left hand is held above her head.
5. A niche composed of two circular pilasters and surmounted by a *makara toraṇa*. It contains an image of four-armed Śiva standing, in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varada-cum-akshamālā*, *triśūla*, *sarpa* broken. He wears *keyuras*, *valayas*, *nūpuras* and a long *mālā* and his lower garment is fastened by a *mekhalā*.
6. A niche composed of two circular pilasters and surmounted by a *makaratoraṇa*. It contains an image of four-armed Śiva standing in *tribhaṅga* and carrying *varada-cum-akshamālā* in his only surviving lower right hand. He wears *jaṭāmukuṭa*, *kuṇḍalas*, *vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *yajñopavita*, *keyuras*, *valayas*, *nūpuras* and a long *mālā* and his lower garment is fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels.
7. A dancing *apsaras* under a spiral lotus-stalk in a recess.
8. An *apsaras* standing under a spiral lotus-stalk in a recess and dancing. Both of her legs have been chopped off.
9. A dancing *apsaras*, under a spiral lotus-stalk in a recess. Her head has been chopped off.
10. A dancing *apsaras*, in a niche composed of the circular pilasters. Her right leg and left breast have been chopped off.

11. A dancing *apsaras*. Her head, left hand and left leg have been chopped off. Her right hand is carried above her head.
12. As *apsaras* standing in *tribhāṅga* in a niche composed of two circular pilaster. Both of her hands have been chopped off.

NICHE ON THE NORTHERN WALL OF THE VESTIBULE

A niche composed of four rectangular pilasters and surmounted by an *udgama* decorated with diamond designs. It contains an image of four-armed Lakshmi seated in *lalitāsana* and carrying *varada-cum-akṣamālā*, *padma*, *padma* and *kalāṣa*. She wears *karaṇḍa-mukuṭa*, *keyūras*, *valayas*, *nūpurās* and a lower garment fastened by a *mekhalā*.

The sanctum measures externally 10.50 mt. long and 7.50 mt. broad. The vestibule measures 7 mts. long and 2.50 mt. broad. The platform in front of the vestibule measures 9 mt. long. The platform is reached by a flight of steps on the east. The floor of the platform and the steps are in a bad state of preservation.

SCULPTURES AND ARCHITECTURAL FRAGMENTS LYING AROUND THE TEMPLE

A number of sculptural and architectural fragments are lying scattered around the temple. They are as follows:—

1. Bust of a bearded ascetic holding a rosary in his right hand. His head and hand have been chopped off. He has moustaches.
2. Eight-armed Gaṇeśa dancing. He holds a serpent by his upper right and left hands. He holds a *modakapātra* in his lowest left hand. His head and remaining hands have been chopped off. He wears *karaṇḍa mukuṭa vaikakshyaka*, *hāra*, *keyuras*, *valayas*, *nūpurās* and lower garment fastened by a *mekhalā* with loops and tassels. A female attendant standing in *tribhāṅga* and carrying *kaṭi* and *kalāṣa* is shown on his right while the mount mouse is portrayed on his left. It is made of white sandstone and datable to c. 11th cen. AD. It measures 2.40 mt. high 1.30 mt. broad and 0.60 mt. thick.
3. A bold *kirtimukha* of white sandstone
4. Seated Gaṇeśa with hands chopped off. It is made of white sandstone
5. An *apsaras* standing under a spiral lotus-stalk and holding a child by her both hands.
6. Four-armed Mahishamardini killing the buffalo demon.

The front portion of the temple has been washed with pink colour by the local people. This should be stopped immediately. The roof of the vestibule rests on

four pilasters. Each pilaster is decorated with *chaitya*-arches and half lotus-medallions. Above the shaft is a capital decorated with flying *bhuta*-brackets.

The temple is a grand specimen of Paramara temple architecture of c. 11th century AD and is under the protection of the department of Archaeology, Govt. of Madhya Pradesh.

REFERENCES

1. P.N. Srivastav, East Nimar District Gazetteer, Bhopal, 1969, p. 468-472
2. Nimar District Gazetteer p. 239, 241.